

Development of an e-learning environment with a user-centered design process: an example in the education of epidemiology and medical statistics

Wieringa TH^{a,b,c1}, van de Belt HA^d, Burgerhof JGM^a, Groen H^a, Postmus D^a, Smidt N^a, Nolte IM^a, Thio CHL^a, la Bastide-van Gemert S^a, Schroevers MJ^e, Ranchor AV^e, Wardenaar KJ^{f,g1}, Hietkamp-Hoekstra SD^d, Nijmeijer R^d, Tamasi K^{a,h}, de Bock GH^a, Snieder H^a, El-Baz N^a

^aUniversity of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Department of Epidemiology, Groningen, The Netherlands

^bDepartment of Health Sciences, Faculty of Science, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

^cUniversity of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Department of Health Sciences, Applied Health Research, Groningen, The Netherlands

^dUniversity of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Wenckebach Institute for Education and Training, Groningen, The Netherlands

^eUniversity of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Department of Health Sciences, Health Psychology, Groningen, The Netherlands

^fUniversity of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, University Center of Psychiatry, Interdisciplinary Center Psychopathology and Emotion regulation, Groningen, The Netherlands

^gUniversity of Groningen, Faculty of Behavioural and Social Sciences, Department of Child and Family Welfare, Groningen, The Netherlands

^hUniversity of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Department of Neurosurgery, Groningen, The Netherlands

¹Present address

Corresponding author

Thomas H. Wieringa

E-mail: t.h.wieringa@umcg.nl

ORCID-ID: 0000-0001-8440-8844

Author contributions

TH Wieringa: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review and editing, Visualization, Project administration

HA van de Belt: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

JGM Burgerhof: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

H Groen: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

D Postmus: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

N Smidt: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

IM Nolte: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

CHL Thio: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

S la Bastide-van Gemert: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

MJ Schroevers: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

AV Ranchor: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

KJ Wardenaar: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

SD Hietkamp-Hoekstra: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

R Nijmeijer: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

K Tamasi: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

GH de Bock: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

H Snieder: Investigation, Writing - review and editing

N El-Baz: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review and editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition

Abstract

Epidemiological and medical statistical skills are essential for healthcare professionals to interpret research results, translate research to clinical practice and thus optimize healthcare. Therefore, these skills are crucial and should be an integral part of medical education. Epidemiological and statistical skills are commonly perceived as being difficult to teach and to learn. A potential solution may be the use of blended learning, which is a mixture of online learning and face-to-face class sessions. Compared to traditional face-to-face class sessions, blended learning has been related to more favorable user satisfaction and performance. We therefore developed an e-learning environment for epidemiology and medical statistics education for students in the faculty of medical sciences, that would be offered to students in combination with traditional face-to-face class sessions. In this paper, we describe the user-centered development process of our e-learning environment. To reach a comprehensive understanding and take into account the needs of the different stakeholders, we carefully identified the distinct stakeholders and their needs, followed by creating modules and videos. To account for the different learning styles that students may have, we also explicitly choose to use several different methods for learning so every student can optimally learn from our e-learning environment. By presenting the development process of our e-learning environment in this paper, we aim to inspire other lecturers, epidemiologists, statisticians and educational program directors to develop e-learning materials, and to support them in this process.

Key words

Epidemiology; statistics; e-learning; blended learning

Statements and declarations

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they do not have any conflicts of interest to disclose.

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1. Introduction

Epidemiology is ‘the study of disease distribution and determinants of disease frequency’ (Rothman, 1976). For example, epidemiology may study the prevalence of type 2 diabetes in a certain population (e.g., a country) and the determinants associated with it (e.g., lifestyle and age). Such research involves the collection and analysis of epidemiological data and hence requires knowledge of statistical methods to be able to describe the study population (graphically and/or numerically) and analyze the relationships between determinants and outcomes (Rothman, 2012). Proficiency in epidemiology and medical statistics is essential for healthcare professionals of all specialties and in all settings to interpret research findings and in turn make optimal decisions in clinical care and provide optimal healthcare (Jayakumar & Umscheid, 2018). Therefore, epidemiology and statistics are crucial and integral to medical education.

Many students, however, perceive learning skills and knowledge of epidemiology and statistics as difficult (Moffat et al, 2004; Milic et al., 2016; Boyle et al., 2014). This causes challenges and opportunities for teachers to develop new learning environments in which these skills can be optimally taught and learned (Milic et al, 2016; Windish et al., 2007; Onwuegbuzie, 2000). New teaching methods like blended learning may offer opportunities to improve learning experiences and subsequently learning outcomes. Blended learning is a mixture of face-to-face class sessions and online learning (Berglund et al., 2015). This mixture tends to be beneficial in terms of user satisfaction and performance (Milic et al., 2016; Means et al., 2013; Evans et al., 2016), probably because it combines the best of both worlds (i.e., online learning and face-to-face class sessions). Face-to-face learning in class offers opportunities for social interaction and direct feedback, while online learning can be more adapted to the individual student (Shute & Towle, 2003): online learning material can deliver the right content, to the right person, at the proper time, in the most appropriate way (National Association of State Boards of Education, 2001).

To create a blended learning environment for students in the faculty of medical sciences (i.e., students in Medicine, Human Movement Sciences, Dentistry and Clinical and Psychosocial Epidemiology (CPE) Research Master), the Department of Epidemiology of the University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG; the Netherlands) took the initiative to develop a new e-learning environment for epidemiology and medical statistics education, aimed to be used in combination with face-to-face class sessions.

In this paper, we carefully describe the user-centered development process of our e-learning environment. The aim of this publication is to inspire other lecturers, epidemiologists, statisticians and educational program directors to develop e-learning materials, and to support them in doing so.

2. Developing the e-learning environment

The Versatest e-learning environment was selected by the e-learning Development Team (EDT), as it was already used within the UMCG for the in-house software development of e-learning tools. Hereby, we aimed to increase the implementation and use of our new e-learning environment. Multiple (inter)national educational institutions have access to the published learning content via a ‘single-sign-on’ connection. Versatest is an e-learning environment, which hosts web-based interactive learning experiences, i.e. learning courses and tests. The software is designed for visual

instruction and features direct feedback that guides the user through the learning content. The learning content can be accessed on any handheld device as well as on a computer. Within the Versatest e-learning environment, a learning portal offers a comprehensive overview of all learning content. The Versatest authoring tool offers lecturers the opportunity to independently create new courses or tests.

The e-learning environment is targeted at four student groups: medical students in their first, second or third year of their bachelors and master students of a dedicated CPE Research Master. The learning materials offered in our e-learning environment consist of two parts: epidemiology and statistics. Both parts are subdivided by level of difficulty. The epidemiology part comprises a basic (for bachelor students) and an advanced (for the CPE Research Master) level. The statistics part is only aimed at students in their bachelor, with different levels of difficulty based on the year in the bachelor program. The materials are in English, so all students can access them. Although the e-learning environment is not targeted at UMCG employees, such as PhD students and junior researchers, the e-learning environment can be assessed and used as a refresher course for employees.

We regard the development process of the advanced epidemiology part to be most interesting for the aim of this paper, as we developed this part from scratch, while we developed the statistics part based on existing materials (e.g., readers). Furthermore, the stakeholders and target groups of the advanced part (i.e., the CPE Research Master students, lecturers, and the CPE Research Master program director) were more extensively and actively involved in developing the advanced epidemiology part compared to the basic epidemiology part. Therefore, we will briefly describe the development of the basic epidemiology and bachelor statistics parts, and subsequently elaborate more extensively on the development of the advanced part.

2.1 Development of the basic epidemiology and bachelor statistics parts

The topics covered in the *basic epidemiological part* are presented in Appendix 1. This part contains videos. Its development process is described in Figure 1. The scripts for the videos were written by an epidemiologists (HG). Several other epidemiologists of the department (GHdB, among others) provided feedback on the initial scripts. The final scripts were transferred to the EDT to create the videos. The epidemiologist who wrote the scripts (HG), one of the project leaders (NEB) and a student panel provided feedback on the (initial and subsequent versions of the) videos. Subsequently, the EDT processed the feedback and created final versions of the videos.

Figure 1 Development process of the basic epidemiology part

For the *bachelor statistical part*, the EDT converted, in collaboration with one of our statisticians (JGMB), a paper-printed reader into web-based modules that contained textual explanations of the theory, illustrations, examples and exercises with worked out answers. The topics covered in the statistical part are presented in Appendix 2. A student assistant, a student in Medicine, checked the modules of year 1 from a students' perspective. The student evaluated both the level, content and language (the student was a native speaker of American English).

2.2 Development of the advanced epidemiology part

After developing the basic and bachelor parts of our e-learning environment, we aimed to take this initiative a step further by developing modules and videos for an advanced epidemiology level. We had to take several steps in this design process, namely: 1) the identification of the stakeholders, 2) the investigation of the stakeholders' needs, and 3) the creation of modules and videos. We elaborate on each of these steps below.

Step 1. Identification of the stakeholders

To meet the stakeholders' needs for developing the e-learning environment, the two project leaders (NEB and THW) identified three groups of stakeholders: 1) *students*, 2) *lecturers* who are responsible for the face-to-face class sessions, and 3) the *CPE Research Master program director*. The students and lecturers are going to use the e-learning environment, whereas the CPE Research Master program director will include (parts of) the e-learning environment in the educational program of the CPE Research Master.

Step 2. Investigation of the stakeholders' needs

To investigate the needs of our students, the project leaders consulted a *panel of student representatives* of the CPE Research Master. The project leaders only consulted CPE Research Master students, as their curriculum covers all the epidemiological topics that are included in the curricula of

the other medical master-programs as well (i.e., Medicine, Human Movement Sciences and Dentistry). Besides the student panel, the project leaders also consulted the *CPE Research Master program director* (AVR) to ensure that the e-learning environment not only covers the topics desired by students, but also the topics that need to be covered as part of their curriculum. The project leaders merged the topic lists of the student representatives panel with the list of their program director. Subsequently, the project leaders selected the most important topics from an epidemiological point of view. After having selected the topics with the highest priority, the project leaders presented this priority list to the *student representatives panel* and the *CPE Research Master program director* to verify whether the list still met their needs. After creation of this final list, the executive project leader (THW) consulted the *lecturers* (represented by HS, DP, GHdB, NS, IMN, CHLT, SIBvG, MJS, KJW and KT) to determine the content and presentation format of each specific topic. The process of investigating the stakeholders' needs is described in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Process of investigating the stakeholders' needs

Step 3. Creation of the text modules and videos

The development process of individual modules and videos is described in Figure 3, which is further explained in the next paragraphs.

Figure 3 Development process of individual modules and videos

Step 3.1 Writing scripts

Based on the lecturer consultations, the executive project leader created one or more scripts per topic. The lecturers provided feedback on the scripts of the topic they teach, so that the scripts are in line with the face-to-face class sessions. In some cases, lecturers preferred to create scripts themselves. In these situations, the development of scripts worked the other way around: lecturers created scripts, and the executive project leader provided feedback on the scripts (e.g., on readability and clarity of the content). The final list of modules and videos is as follows:

Study designs

- How to select a suitable study design to answer my research question? (An introduction to study designs)
- Cross-sectional studies
- Case-control studies
- Cohort studies
- Randomized Controlled Trials

Missing data

- Introduction to missing data
- Missing data mechanisms
- Strategies for minimizing missing data
- Assumptions and techniques for imputation
- Multiple imputation in R
- Multiple imputation in SPSS

Risk of bias

- Strategies to minimize the risk of bias in RCTs

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses

- Systematic reviews and meta-analyses

Measuring concepts

- Introduction to measuring concepts
- Measuring concepts: Developing a measurement instrument
- Measuring concepts: Assessing the validity of a measurement instrument
- Measuring concepts: Assessing the reliability of a measurement instrument
- Measuring concepts: Assessing the responsiveness of a measurement instrument
- Measuring concepts: Interpretability

Sample size calculation

- Sample size calculation

Longitudinal data analysis

- Introduction to longitudinal data analysis

R

- Introduction to R
- Why you should use R
- Introduction into RStudio
- Creating variables in R
- Data types in R
- Combining data in R
- Extracting data in R
- Creating functions in R

Confounding

- Confounding

In the scripts, we paid special attention to meeting the needs of students' different *learning styles* (Felder & Silverman, 1988). Learning styles refer to students' preferred ways to learn, such as more inductive or deductive, and these can play an important role in e-learning systems (Truong, 2016) as differences in learning styles affect what students learn in an instructional setting (Shute & Towle,

2003). Examples of methods we used to meet the needs of students' different learning styles are presented in Table 1 (Felder, 1988).

Table 1. Examples of methods to serve learning styles within our e-learning environment (Felder, 1988)

Learning style dimension	Learning style	Examples of teaching styles within our e-learning environment
Perception	Intuitive learning style	Presenting the context of the topic at the start of a module or video (e.g., we provided the level of evidence pyramid in the introduction of every video about study designs and we presented the COSMIN-taxonomy (Mokkink et al., 2010) in the introduction of every module about measuring concepts)
	Sensory learning style	Providing specific examples of the theory
Organization	Inductive learning style	Offering examples (in combination with theoretical explanation)
	Deductive learning style	Offering theoretical explanation, with support of examples
Input	Auditory learning style	Support videos with voice-overs to explain theory
	Visual learning style	Using text and videos to explain theory and support written theory (where possible) with images and illustrations
Processing	Reflective learning style	- Presenting text (in modules) to explain theory - Presenting videos to explain theory
	Active learning style	Including formative assessments
Understanding	Sequential learning style	Presenting the modules and videos in sequential order, based on level of difficulty (i.e., from basic to advanced (epidemiology) and from bachelor year 1 to year 3 (statistics))
	Global learning style	Offering the possibility to use the module and video independently of each other

In general, we used text modules for topics that have a more mathematical character (e.g., clinimetrics and missing data) and videos for topics that aim to explain more conceptual aspects (e.g., different study designs).

Step 3.2 Converting scripts into text modules and videos

When both the executive project leader and the lecturer agreed on a final version of the script, the former sent the script to members of the EDT (represented by SDHH, HAvdB and RN). The EDT then created the initial text modules and videos. Subsequently, the executive project leader and lecturer provided feedback on these first versions of the modules and videos. Thereafter, the EDT processed this feedback. We repeated this cycle of providing feedback and adjusting the modules and videos, as an iterative development process, until all parties (i.e., the executive project leader, lecturer and EDT) agreed on the final version.

Step 3.3 Evaluating modules and videos

After developing the modules and videos, the project leaders and members of the EDT consulted the student representatives panel with the aim of testing the final versions of the modules and videos. The student representatives panel was consulted by going through the modules and videos, and filling out an online questionnaire, as preparation for a group meeting. During this group meeting, the student representatives panel gave their feedback to the project leaders and the EDT. Through discussion during the group meeting, the student representatives panel, the project leaders and the EDT together decided how to adjust the modules and videos. Subsequently, the EDT adjusted the modules and videos where deemed necessary.

Importantly, we keep evaluating and improving the e-learning environment through an iterative process. In this process, students and lecturers have the opportunity to provide feedback through periodic qualitative educational evaluations and/or by e-mailing one of the project leaders (NEB). Subsequently, this project leader will discuss the feedback with the EDT. Together, they decide how to best improve the e-learning environment based on the feedback.

3. Conclusion

In collaboration with our identified stakeholders, we developed an e-learning environment for epidemiology and medical statistics education. With this, we aim to support lecturers in creating a blended learning environment, from which students may benefit when learning about epidemiology and medical statistics (Milic et al., 2016; Means et al., 2013; Evans et al., 2016). The e-learning environment uses different methods to satisfy students' different learning styles, so that every student can optimally learn from it. Now that our e-learning environment is active, we encourage lecturers to incorporate it in their educational practice and our students to use it. We also invite lecturers and students to provide feedback, which we can use to make further improvements. The feedback from lecturers seems to be as important as that from students as lecturers' attitude towards the e-learning environment, their teaching style and their control over the e-learning environment affects the students' learning outcomes (Webster & Hackley, 1997). Besides to the initial end-users, the e-learning environment is also open to be used by UMCG employees (e.g., PhD students and researchers) and students of regular master programs as a refresher of epidemiological and statistical knowledge.

With this paper, we hope to inspire other lecturers and educational leaders to develop e-learning materials and to support them in their efforts. Through a user-centered development process we aim to meet the needs and desires of the end-users (i.e., students, researchers and lecturers). Needs and desires of students are potentially even more met by incorporating opportunities to learn through different learning style dimensions.

References

1. Berglund A, Leander K, Modig K, Stenbeck M, Alfredsson L. Online learning in an epidemiology curriculum. In proceedings of *E-Learn: World conference on e-Learning in corporate, government, healthcare, and higher education*; 2015, October 19; Kona, Hawaii, United States of America. San Diego, California, United States of America: Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). p.272-277.
2. Boyle EA, MacArthur EW, Connolly TM, Hainey T, Manea M, Kärki A, et al. A narrative literature review of games, animations and simulations to teach research methods and statistics. *Comput Educ* 2014;74:1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.01.004>
3. Evans KH, Thompson AC, O'Brien C, Bryant M, Basaviah P, Prober C, et al. An innovative blended preclinical curriculum in clinical epidemiology and biostatistics: Impact on student satisfaction and performance. *Acad Med* 2016;91(5):696-700. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000001085>
4. Felder RM, Silverman LK. Learning and teaching styles in engineering education. *Engr Education* 1988;78(7):674-81.
5. Jayakumar KL, Umscheid CA. Expanding epidemiology and biostatistics curricula in undergraduate medical education to promote evidence-based practice. *BMJ Evid Based Med* 2018;23(3):117. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjebm-2018-110951>
6. Means B, Toyama Y, Murphy R, Baki M. The effectiveness of online and blended learning: A meta-analysis of the empirical literature. *Teach Col Rec* 2013;115(3):1-47. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146811311500307>
7. Milic NM, Trajkovic GZ, Bukumiric ZM, Cirkovic A, Nikolic IM, Milin JS, et al. Improving education in medical statistics: Implementing a blended learning model in the existing curriculum. *PLoS One* 2016;11(2):e0148882. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148882>
8. Moffat M, Sinclair HK, Cleland JA, Smith WCS, Taylor RJ. Epidemiology teaching: Student and tutor perceptions. *Med Teach* 2004;26(8):691-5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590400013537>
9. Mokkink L, Terwee C, Patrick D, Alonso J, Stratford P, Knol D, et al. International consensus on taxonomy, terminology, and definitions of measurement properties for health-related patient-reported outcomes: Results of the COSMIN study. *J Clin Epidemiol* 2010;63:737-745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.02.006>
10. National Association of State Boards of Education. Any time, any place, any path, any pace. *The report of the NASBE study group on e-learning: The future of education*. ERIC Clearinghouse; 2001. 55 p.

11. Onwuegbuzie AJ. Attitudes toward statistics assessments. *Assess Eval High Educ* 2000;25(4):321-39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/713611437>
12. Rothman KJ. Causes. *Am J Epidemiol* 1976;104(6):587-92.
13. Rothman KJ. *Epidemiology: An introduction*. 2nd ed. New York: Oxford University Press;2012.
14. Shute V, Towle B. Adaptive e-learning. *Educ Psychol* 2003;38(2):105-14.
15. Truong HM. Integrating learning styles and adaptive e-learning system: Current developments, problems and opportunities. *Comput Human Behav* 2016;55:1185-93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.02.014>
16. Webster J, Hackley P. Teaching effectiveness in technology-mediated distance learning. *Acad Manage J* 1997;40(6):1282-309. <https://doi.org/10.5465/257034>
17. Windish DM, Huot SJ, Green ML. Medicine residents' understanding of the biostatistics and results in the medical literature. *JAMA* 2007;298(9):1010-22. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.298.9.1010>

Appendix 1 – Module and videos incorporated in the basic epidemiology part

Year 1:

- Introduction to Epidemiology (module, which contains the following videos):
 - Incidence and prevalence
 - Odds ratio and relative risk
 - Study designs
 - Screening, sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values

Year 2:

- Validity and precision
- Generalizability
- Bias
- Confounding , interaction, and stratification

Year 3: None

Appendix 2 – Modules incorporated in the bachelor statistics part

Year 1:

- Module 1: Introduction
- Module 2: Descriptive statistics
- Module 3: Probabilities
- Module 4: Probability distribution
- Module 5: Estimation and confidence interval
- Module 6: Hypothesis testing
- Module 7: Independent T-test and One-way ANOVA
- Module 8: Pearson's Chi-square and Fisher's exact test
- Module 9: Non-parametric tests for independent groups
- Module 10: Statistical test for paired observations
- Module 11: Correlation
- Module 12: Overview statistical tests

Year 2:

- Module 1: Introduction regression analysis
- Module 2: Simple linear regression with a continuous explanatory variable
- Module 3: Simple linear regression with a binary explanatory variable
- Module 4: Simple linear regression with a categorical explanatory variable with more than two categories
- Module 5: Multiple linear regression
- Module 6: Interactions in linear regression
- Module 7: Simple logistic regression
- Module 8: Multiple logistic regressions
- Module 9: Overview regression
- Module 10: Building regression models

Year 3:

- Module 1: Sample size calculations
- Module 2: Introduction to survival analysis, the Kaplan Meier curve and some descriptive statistics
- Module 3: The log-rank test
- Module 4: Cox regression